

Women Entrepreneurship and Regional Development: An Overview

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Vatsala, A. "Women Entrepreneurship and Regional Development: An Overview." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 11–15.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2563751>

A.Vatsala

Head of the Department of Commerce, Annai Women's College, Karur

Abstract

Women are goal oriented, independent, flexible, tolerant, creative, realistic, enthusiastic and energetic because of which the management style differs from their male counterpart. Women are by and large born managers as they manage their house. They can simultaneously do more than one task at a time and have good coordination skills. They invariably think of entering a business once their children are grown up and household responsibilities get reduced. Women rely on their own finance and avoid availing of loans. Any woman who generates business idea, sets up an organisation, combines the factors of production, operates the unit, undertakes risks and handles the problem involved in managing a business enterprise that is called as women entrepreneur.

Introduction

Entrepreneur the word entrepreneur finds its origin in a French word "entreprendre", which means "to undertake." During early 16th century, the term was used for the persons engaged in military expeditions. The word entrepreneur is given as a person 'who starts a business'. It also adds that an entrepreneur is a person 'who starts an enterprise, business or a firm'.

According to Cole "entrepreneurship is the purposeful activity of an individual or a group of associated individuals undertaken to initiate, maintain and increase profits by production or distribution of economic goods and services". Entrepreneurship involves the combination of capital, technology and talent. It is a dynamic process which involves risks.

The Government of India has defined women entrepreneurs based on women's participation in equity and employment of a business enterprise. A women entrepreneurship is defined as an enterprise owned and controlled by a woman having a minimum financial interest of 51% of the capital and giving at least 51% of the employment generated in the enterprise to a woman.

Regional Development is a broad term but can be seen as a general effort to reduce regional disparities by supporting (employment and wealth-generating) economic activity in regions. In the past, regional development policy tended to try to achieve these objectives by means of large-scale infrastructure development and by attracting

investment. Past policies have failed to reduce regional disparities significantly and have not been able to help individual lagging regions to catch up, despite the allocation of significant public funding. The result is under-used economic potential and weakened social cohesion.

Functions Of Women Entrepreneur

A Women entrepreneur has to perform all the functions. These include idea generation, screening, determination of objectives, project preparation, product analysis, determination of forms of business organization, completion of formal activities, raising funds, procuring men machine materials and operations of business.

Five Functions of a Women Entrepreneur's:

1. The prospects of starting a new business enterprise.
2. Undertaking a risk and handling of economic uncertainties.
3. Introduction of innovations, imitations of innovations.
4. Coordination, administration and control.
5. Supervision and leadership.

Challenges and Problems Faced By Women Entrepreneurs

Problem of Finance: To raise finance, they do not have properties in their names to use them as collateral securities. Thus, their access to external sources of funds is restricted.

Limited Mobility: Due to primary household responsibilities towards her family, her time gets divided between the two worlds. Thus, her mobility is restricted. This also has an implication on business.

Lack of Education: Women have lower rate of literacy. Nearly 60% of the women are illiterate in India, because of which they are not aware of the latest developments that have taken place in technology.

Male dominated society: A women is dominated by men in her family as well as business. Her freedom is restricted. She always has to consult and get the approval of men.

Low risk-bearing ability: From the childhood, her parents take decisions for her and after marriage her husband takes over.

Social recognition: Society does not give due recognition to women entrepreneurs. They are looked down as small and weak.

Family restriction: Women are expected to spend more time with their family members. They do not encourage women to travel business opportunities.

Role Conflict: Marriage and family life are given more importance than career and social life in Indian society.

Lack of persistent Nature: Women generally have sympathy for others. They are very emotional.

Lack of Information: Women entrepreneurs are not generally aware of the subsidies and incentives available for them. Lack of knowledge may prevent them from availing the special schemes.

Women in Business

Women entrepreneurs have introduced new ideas, methods and objects for the welfare of the society. The following are some of the leading women entrepreneurs in India.

- Mrs.Santhiduraisamy of Sakthi Masala is the backbone for the success of SAKTHI MASALA. Today if Sakthi Masala is No.1, it is because of maintaining product superiority, through sophisticated machinery and the expertise of the trained personnel. Sakthi Masala employs

over 800 dynamic, hardworking skilled and unskilled workers, professionals, scientists and consultants.

- Among the most enterprising women putting India on the world map is Vandana Shiva, Ph.D. The globally known scientist and environmentalist started Navdanya. The purpose of the organisation is to support local farmers, rescue and conserve crops and plants that are being pushed to extinction and make those crops available through direct marketing.

Business Opportunities for Women Entrepreneurs

Today most of the women entrepreneurs are found in carrying out business like beauty parlours, tailoring shops, boutiques, preparation of food items etc. some of them are as follows:

- | | |
|-----------------------------|--|
| 1. Food Processing | 19. Desk Top Publishing |
| 2. Bakery | 20. Textile Design Printing and Dying |
| 3. Tailoring and Embroidery | 21. Nylon Fishnet |
| 4. Mineral Based Products | 22. Electrical Home Appliance Repairing |
| 5. Simple Chemicals | 23. Fruit Packing |
| 6. Pharmaceuticals | 24. Umbrella Assembling |
| 7. Handicraft | 25. Fish Pickles |
| 8. Fashion Design | 26. Hosiery Garments |
| 9. Cosmetology | 27. Electrical and Electronic Equipment repair |
| 10. Readymade Garments | 28. Coir Products |
| 11. Envelope Making | 29. Woven Fabrics |
| 12. Printing and Binding | 30. Elastic Tape and Nylon Tape |
| 13. Screen Printing | 31. Lamination |
| 14. Data Processing | 32. Manufacture of Toys |
| 15. Circuit Board Making | 33. Small Transformer |
| 16. Plastic Reprocessing | 34. Mushroom Cultivation |
| 17. Power Laundry | 35. TV and Radio Repairing |
| 18. Soft wear Development | 36. Beauty Parlour |

Institutional Support For Women Entrepreneurial Development

In India, both Government and Non-Government Organizations (NGO) render their services in promoting women entrepreneurs. Some of the institutions that render support to women entrepreneurs are as follows:

I - Commerical Bank

Many of the scheduled commercial banks provide counselling to women entrepreneurs mostly in the small scale and a few of them provide merchant banking services to the corporate sector.

- Bank of Baroda provides Entrepreneurial Banking
- Bank of India scheme offers in selection of industry, project preparation, market survey etc.,
- Canara Bank provides Industrial information and guidance services to provide information and advice to its clients.
- Indian Bank provides Entrepreneur Advisory Services – Marketing is provided through the personnel of the bank and panels of experts.
- Indian Overseas Bank provides small business opportunities. Who wish to start a business.

Schemes available with commercial banks

1. Cash credit scheme provides funding arrangement of a major percentage on the value of raw material, work in process, finished goods and receivable.
2. Working capital finance schemes helps the women entrepreneurs to meet their working capital requirements through
 - Venture Capital funding
 - Factoring
 - Discounting of Sales Bills
 - Letter of Credit facility
 - Fixed Capital Finance Schemes
 1. Term Loan
 2. Lease finance
 3. Hire purchase finance
 4. Suppliers bill discounting scheme
 5. Deferred payment credit scheme

II – Tamil Nadu Corporation for Development of Women

Special schemes available for women entrepreneurs

1. Women Self Help Group Special Schemes
2. National Equity Fund Scheme
3. Small Industry Development Bank of India Scheme
4. Bank of India's Priyadarshini Yojana

III – Government Schemes

1. Prime Minister's Rozgar Yojana (PMRY)
2. Self Employment Programme for Urban Poor (SEPUP)
3. Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP)

Rural Entrepreneurship

About 80% of India's population lives in rural areas. If India has to develop well, villages have to develop well. Gandhiji had realised and recognised this fact and encouraged Khadi and Village industries.

Village industries have been grouped into seven categories:

1. Mineral based
2. Forest based
3. Agro based
4. Polymer and chemical
5. Engineering and non-conventional
6. Textiles including Khadi
7. Service industry

Top Priority to Develop Rural Industries in India

- The reduction in migration of rural population to urban areas.
- Balanced regional growth
- Reducing rural-urban gap
- Increasing rural income
- Reducing the heritage of the country
- Reduction the urban pollution
- Higher economic growth

Problems of Rural Entrepreneurship

Development rural entrepreneurship is not an easy task. There are lot of difficulties

- Domination by agricultural mindset
- Lack of education with low literacy
- Poor infrastructure because of which access is difficult and costly
- Lack of information
- Lack of quality control
- Language barriers
- High input cost due to transportation
- Inadequate finance and credit
- Lack of awareness and knowledge about the opportunities
- Preference for salaried jobs than self-employment

Conclusion

Entrepreneurship provides employment and source of earning to people. It helps in reducing the monopoly of rich businessman and achieving a balanced regional development and growth in economy. Government of India is conducting development programmes to identify entrepreneurial potential and assistance from financial and non-financial institutions are being provided to entrepreneur. Entrepreneurship training institutes have been established and financial and operational support is being provided to young entrepreneurs in India.

References

- Ronstadt, RC. "Entrepreneurship, Dover, MA". *Lord Publishing Co.*.P. 28, 1984.
- Naidu, NVR & Rao, TK. "Management and Entrepreneurship", New Delhi: *I.K International Publishing House*, P. 179. 2008.
- Onuoha, G. "Entrepreneurship", *AIST International Journal*. vol. 10, pp. 20-32. 2007.